

Search for Potential Antitumour Compounds. Part III. Synthesis of Some N^α -Ethoxycarbonylamino-acid- N^2N^2 -bis-(2-chloroethyl)hydrazides

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Several mustards of hydrazides of N -ethoxycarbonylamino-acids have been synthesised with a view to testing their antitumour activity.

N^1N^1 -Bis-(2-chloroethyl)hydrazine is a reactive alkylating agent with definite tumour-growth inhibitory activity¹. Acylation of the free amino group reduces the alkylating property and the hydrazides are not biologically active *in vitro*, but regain their activity when hydrolysed back to the bis-(2-chloroethyl)hydrazine by the proteolytic enzymes present in cancer cells². The urethanes (or N -ethoxycarbonylamines), on the other hand, are known to produce proteolytic enzymes in cancer cells³⁻⁴. Based on these observations and using amino-acids as biological "carriers" for introduction of toxic residues for cellular metabolism⁵⁻⁷, several N^α -ethoxycarbonylamino-acid- N^2N^2 -bis-(2-chloroethyl)hydrazides of type (I) have been synthesised.

For preparation of these compounds, amino-acid esters were at first refluxed with N^1N^1 -bis-(2-hydroxyethyl)hydrazine and the resulting amino-acid- N^2N^2 -bis-(2-hydroxyethyl)hydrazide (II) was converted to its ethoxycarbonyl derivative (III) by the action of ethyl chloroformate in anhydrous ethanol and anhydrous potassium carbonate. Treatment of this amino-acid hydrazide with thionyl chloride furnished the required mustard derivatives (I).

1. Preussmann *et al.*, *Angew. Chem.*, 1958, **70**, 743.
2. Ishidate *et al.*, *Chem. Pharm. Bull. Tokyo*, 1960, **8**, 543.
3. Danielli, *Ann. Rep. Brit. Emp. Cancer camp.*, 1958, **36**, 527.
4. Danielli, Centennial Lectures Commemorating the 100th anniversary of E. R. Squibb and Sons, ed. by J. T. Culbertson, p. 167, New York, Putnam.
5. Bergel, *Ann. N. Y. Acad. Sci.*, 1958, **68**, 1238.
6. Ishidate *et al.*, *J. Amer. Pharm. Assoc.*, 1955, **44**, 132.
7. Nyalan and Busch, *Chem. & Eng. News*, 1959, May 5, p.48.

*EXPERIMENTAL

Amino-acid esters were prepared by the method of Kupryozewski *et al.*⁸. *N*¹*N*²-Bis-(2-hydroxyethyl)hydrazine was prepared by the method of Ishidate *et al.*²

*Amino-acid-N*¹*N*²-bis-(2-hydroxyethyl)hydrazides (II).—Ethyl ester of the amino-acid (0.01*M*), *N*¹*N*²-bis-(2-hydroxyethyl)hydrazine (0.01*M*), and anhydrous ethanol (20 ml) were refluxed for 6 hr. on a water bath. The reaction mixture was then concentrated to half its volume and left overnight in the cold when colorless needles separated. After filtration these were recrystallised from anhydrous ethanol. The yields, m.p., and analyses of hydrazides (II) prepared are recorded in Table. I.

TABLE I

No.	Amino-acid residue.	M.P.	% Yield.	Formula.	% Nitrogen.	
					Found.	Reqd.
1	Glycine	137°	62	C ₆ H ₁₃ O ₃ N ₃	23.1	23.2
2	Alanine	120°	60	C ₇ H ₁₇ O ₃ N ₃	22.1	21.9
3	α-Aminoisobutyric	158°	72	C ₈ H ₁₉ O ₃ N ₃	20.1	20.5
4	α-Amino- <i>n</i> -butyric	161°	56	C ₈ H ₁₉ O ₃ N ₃	20.0	20.5
5	α-Amino- <i>n</i> -valeric	162°	98	C ₉ H ₂₁ O ₃ N ₃	19.0	19.2
6	Valine	167°	70	C ₉ H ₂₁ O ₃ N ₃	19.1	19.2
7	Leucine	178°	49	C ₁₀ H ₂₃ O ₃ N ₃	18.2	18.0
8	Isoleucine	197°	36	C ₁₀ H ₂₃ O ₃ N ₃	17.7	18.0
9	Glutamic acid	156°	87	C ₁₃ H ₂₅ O ₆ N ₃	20.2	19.9
10	α-Phenylglycine	217°	32	C ₁₂ H ₁₉ O ₃ N ₃	16.8	16.9
11	Tyrosine	227°	39	C ₁₃ H ₂₁ O ₄ N ₃	14.8	14.9

N^α-Ethoxycarbonylamino acid-*N*¹*N*²-bis-(2-hydroxyethyl)hydrazides (III).—A mixture of the hydrazide (II) (0.007*M*), ethyl chloroformate (0.007*M*), anhydrous ethanol (35 ml), and anhydrous potassium carbonate (5 g.) was refluxed for 1 hr. and then cooled and filtered. Concentration of the filtrate provided the ethoxycarbonyl derivative (III) as colorless needles which were recrystallised from anhydrous ethanol. The yields, m.p., and analyses of the ethoxycarbonyl derivatives prepared are recorded in Table II.

TABLE II

*No.	M.P.	% Yield.	Formula.	% Nitrogen.		*No.	M.P.	% Yield.	Formula.	% Nitrogen.	
				Found.	Reqd.					Found.	Reqd.
1	58°	40	C ₉ H ₁₉ O ₅ N ₃	17.2	16.9	7	75°	76	C ₁₉ H ₂₇ O ₅ N ₃	13.7	13.8
2	72°	55	C ₁₀ H ₂₁ O ₅ N ₃	15.6	16.0	8	82°	80	C ₁₃ H ₂₇ O ₅ N ₃	13.6	13.8
3	58°	72	C ₁₁ H ₂₃ O ₅ N ₃	15.4	15.1	9	93°	60	C ₁₆ H ₃₃ O ₈ N ₃	16.9	16.9
4	67°	79	C ₁₁ H ₂₃ O ₅ N ₃	15.1	15.1	10	117°	39	C ₁₅ H ₂₃ O ₅ N ₃	13.2	12.9
5	110°	62	C ₁₂ H ₂₅ O ₅ N ₃	14.2	14.4	11	110°	35	C ₁₆ H ₂₅ O ₆ N ₃	12.1	11.8
6	103°	52	C ₁₂ H ₂₅ O ₅ N ₃	14.2	14.4						

N. B. Number of the amino-acid residues corresponds to those in Table I.

*All m.p.s are uncorrected.

8. *Acta Biochem. Polon.*, 1957, 4, 85.

N α -*l*-thoxycarbonylamino-acid-*N*²*N*²-bis-(2-chloroethyl)hydrazides (I).— *N* α -Ethoxycarbonylhydrazide (III) (0.005*M*) and thionyl chloride (0.015*M*) were mixed together and kept overnight. The mixture was then heated on a water bath and excess of thionyl chloride removed under reduced pressure. Repeated recrystallisations of the semisolid mass from chloroform furnished the required *N* α -ethoxycarbonylamino-acid-*N*²*N*²-bis-(2-chloroethyl)hydrazide (I). The yields, m.p., and analyses of the mustard derivatives prepared are recorded in Table III.

TABLE III

Sl. No.	m.P.	% Yield.	Formula.	% Carbon.		% Hydrogen.		% Nitrogen.	
				Found.	Reqd.	Found.	Reqd.	Found.	Reqd.
1	187°	68	C ₉ H ₁₇ O ₃ N ₃ Cl ₂	-	-	-	-	15.0	14.7
2	179°	42	C ₁₀ H ₁₉ O ₃ N ₃ Cl ₂	-	-	-	-	13.9	14.0
3	201°	47	C ₁₁ H ₂₁ O ₃ N ₃ Cl ₂	-	-	-	-	13.3	13.4
4	219°	45	C ₁₁ H ₂₁ O ₃ N ₃ Cl ₂	-	-	-	-	13.1	13.4
5	217°	49	C ₁₂ H ₂₃ O ₃ N ₃ Cl ₂	44.2	43.9	7.0	7.0	13.0	12.8
6	227	38	C ₁₂ H ₂₃ O ₃ N ₃ Cl ₂	43.8	43.9	6.9	7.0	12.6	12.8
7	201°	26	C ₁₃ H ₂₅ O ₃ N ₃ Cl ₂	45.2	45.9	7.0	7.3	12.0	12.3
8	176°	38	C ₁₃ H ₂₅ O ₃ N ₃ Cl ₂	46.1	45.9	7.8	7.3	12.3	12.3
9	156°	28	C ₁₆ H ₂₉ O ₄ N ₃ Cl ₄	38.8	38.6	5.5	5.8	15.1	14.9
10	227°	35	C ₁₅ H ₂₇ O ₃ N ₃ Cl ₂	48.2	49.7	6.0	5.8	11.1	11.3
11	222°	31	C ₁₆ H ₂₉ O ₄ N ₃ Cl ₂	48.7	49.0	5.8	5.9	10.4	10.7

N.B. Number of the amino-acid residues correspond to those in Table I.

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